

Studies directed toward the synthesis of the C₁₅-C₂₁ fragment of (-)-discodermolide

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Manuscript received 30 October 2000

A novel method developed by us recently for the synthesis of chiral 2-methyl-1,3-diols by radical-mediated diastereoselective opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols at the more substituted carbon serves as the key step in our studies directed toward the stereoselective synthesis of the C₁₅-C₂₁ fragment of (-)-discodermolide.

Discodermolide (1), a highly potent antimetabolic agent was isolated from the Caribbean sponge *Discodermia dissoluta*¹. Its mechanism of action similar to that of taxol by stabilizing microtubules and promoting the polymerization of tubulin makes it a promising candidate for cancer chemotherapy²⁻⁵. The molecule with 13 stereocentres and a number of unique structural features has been a challenging target to synthetic organic chemists. Already, three total syntheses of the natural (+)-discodermolide⁶⁻⁸, three syntheses of the antipodal (-)-discodermolide⁹⁻¹¹ and several synthetic approaches¹²⁻²⁵ have been reported.

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Scheme 2 delineates the actual synthetic steps followed

In this paper, we describe our studies directed toward the synthesis of the C₁₅-C₂₁ fragment 2 of (-)-discodermolide. The total syntheses of discodermolide from intermediates very similar to 2 have already been reported^{7,10}. The salient feature of our synthesis is the assembling of all the five stereocentres in 2 from a single chiral precursor, methyl (*R*)-(-)-3-hydroxy-2-methylpropionate (3), following a convergent strategy in which a novel method developed by us recently for the synthesis of chiral 2-methyl-1,3-diols by radical-mediated diastereoselective opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols at the more substituted carbon served as the key step²⁶. This reaction was expected to provide the chiral '2-methyl-1,3-diol' moiety of the C₁₇-C₁₉ segment of the molecule, with the remaining two stereocentres of 2 originating from the chiral precursor 3.

Retrosynthetic analysis of 2 (Scheme 1) reveals that it can be prepared from the diol 4 which, in turn, was ex-

pected to be the product of our radical-mediated epoxide opening reaction with the trisubstituted *syn*-epoxy alcohol 5. Diastereoselective epoxidation of the allylic alcohol 6 was planned to synthesize 5. The allylic alcohol 6 was expected to be the product in the diastereoselective hydride reduction of the α,β -unsaturated ketone intermediate 7. Horner-Emmons olefination was the method of choice to prepare 7 by coupling the aldehyde 8 and the keto phosphonate 9, both of which could originate from the common precursor 3.

Scheme 2 delineates the actual synthetic steps followed by us in our studies directed toward the stereoselective synthesis of 2. Silylation of 3 gave the protected intermediate 10 in 92% yield, which was reacted with the anion generated from diethyl ethylphosphonate on treatment with *n*-BuLi. Horner-Emmons olefination of the resulting ketophosphonate 9 with the aldehyde 8, prepared from 3 in two steps, PMB-protection, followed by DIBAL-H reduction, furnished the (*E*)- α,β -unsaturated ketone 7. Diastereoselective hydride reduction of the ketone using DIBAL-H in toluene at -78° gave the *anti*-product 6 as the only isomer in 80% yield. Epoxidation of the allylic alcohol 6 with *m*-CPBA furnished both the expected *syn*-(5) and the unwanted *anti*-(11) epoxy alcohols in almost equal amounts in 82% yield. The isomers were separated by silica gel column chromatography. The stereochemistry of the isomers were assigned on the basis of ¹H NMR studies and subsequently verified after 2 steps : opening up of the epoxy rings

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis of 2.

and making acetonides from the resulting diols. The ^{13}C NMR signals of the acetonides were used to confirm the C_{17} - C_{19} stereochemical relationships of the diols and hence, of the starting epoxy alcohols.

With the requisite trisubstituted epoxy alcohols in hand, the stage was now set to try out our radical-mediated opening reaction. The *anti*-epoxy alcohol **11** was the first isomer chosen for carrying out the key reaction. When **11** was treated

with Cp_2TiCl and cyclohexa-1,4-diene according to the procedure reported by us earlier²⁶, the expected product **13** was formed only as a minor product, the major one being an unwanted olefin **12** with the combined yield of 60% and product ratio of 4 : 1. This is the second time²⁷ that such a product is formed in this type of reaction which otherwise has always given us the targeted 2-methyl-1,3-diols^{28,29}.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the acetonide from the mi-

Scheme 2. Studies directed toward the synthesis of 2.

nor product **13** showed acetone methyl signals at δ 25.54 and 23.51 and that of ketal carbon at 100.3 ppm, proving C₁₇-C₁₉-*anti* relationship in the diol **13**^{30,31}. This proved that the starting epoxy alcohol **11** was the *anti*-isomer. The configuration of the C₁₈ proton has not been determined yet. The major olefinic product **12** was next treated with DDQ under anhydrous conditions to get the 6-membered PMP-acetal **14** in 70% yield³². Diastereoselective reduction of the olefin function using H₂ and 10% Pd on carbon as catalyst in the presence of 0.5 eq. NH₄OAc³³ gave **15** with α -methyl as the major isomer (3 : 1 ratio). The small value (2 Hz) of $J_{17,18}$ supports the assigned stereochemistry.

Next, we turned our attention to the requisite *syn*-epoxy alcohol **5**. When compound **5** was subjected to cp₂TiCl-cyclohexa-1,4-diene, the only product that could be isolated was the unwanted olefin **16**. Efforts are now on to convert **16** to the targeted fragment of discodermolide **2** following the same chemistry described above for the conversion of **12** to **15**. Further work is under progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for Research Fellowship to one of them (P.L.) and for CSIR Young Scientist Award Research Grant to the other (T.K.C.).

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